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Mission (im)possible? Teaching social sciences to engineering students

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ABSTRACT

This paper explores the challenges of teaching social sciences to engineering students. While discussing this topic is hardly new, the challenges Industry 4.0 will bring makes it more acute. The rationale of this study is twofold: on the one hand it seems that employees' social skills are in short supply but in growing demand, on the other hand the suggestion to include social sciences into engineering education has a long history but less success so far.

The study's overarching hypothesis is that engineering students are perceiving social sciences as less relevant and useful for the engineering career. The research question was focused on how the engineering students perceive the relevance of social sciences to engineering, and how social sciences should be taught and assessed. The survey was applied to undergraduate and master students enrolled in engineering programmes of a British university between 2017 and 2019.

The conclusions outline the engineering students' perceptions and expectations. They suggests that the actual engineering curricula fails to make engineering students understand the need for social skills. Many of the students feel that social sciences could be helpful, but they would prefer non-compulsory and not-assessed training sessions. Neither the differences between social sciences and natural sciences, nor the impact of social sciences education on individual skills are not well understood.

In conclusion it is essential to revisit not only the content but also how non-technical knowledge is delivered to engineering students, and also how their expectations regarding what makes a good engineer are informed and managed.

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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Rationale

The rationale of this exploratory study is twofold: on the one hand it seems that employees' social skills currently are in short supply but the demand is permanently growing. On the other hand, the current experience suggests that teaching social sciences topics to engineering students is rather a difficult task.

The suggestion to include social sciences and humanities into engineering education has a long history. Giebelhaus [1] enumerated various reports demanding it starting with 1930 Wickenden Commission Report. At the beginning this sort of suggestion was based on the engineers' need to deal with people. In 1968 the American Society for Engineering Education (ASEE) report showed that the American engineer was more and more becoming involved in administrative decision-making and policy-making positions, 50% of those replying to ASEE's study indicated that their functions were at least half administrative [2].

Almost three decades later Wenk was pointing in the same direction: 'While hardware components require expert knowledge, the delivery system fundamentally requires a general knowledge of business, public management, the social context, and human behavior. Put another way, the sum of sophisticated but narrow grooves of technical know-how do not add up to a working model of human society' [3]. Wenk was arguing that narrow engineering knowledge is essential in the modern society but it is simply insufficient to run successfully the more and more complex social systems such as industrial organisations.

More recently, the European Union's Future & Emerging Technologies Advisory Group report observed in 2016 that the integration of social sciences with engineering has been patchy, and in large areas of Horizon 2020 is either not present or merely paid lip service [4]. All these and many other reports and studies suggest that while the case has been made for almost a century, the success of this endeavour seems to be still out of reach.

1.2 Social sciences in engineering education

In a seminal study Davis Noble (1997) argued that engineering can be seen as the link between two forces that have shaped modern American society — the scientific technology and corporate capitalism [5]. From a slightly Marxist perspective, Noble argues that engineering has institutionalised the science into the service of corporate capital. Engineering education, which is the aspect of interest for this discussion, is one of the multiple ways in which this relation has been institutionalised. However, the last decades witnessed the reducing of the engineers' role and position within corporations.

Few years later on, Wenk observed that 'corporations, which used to have many engineers on their boards of directors, today are composed mainly of MBAs and lawyers. Few engineers hold public office or even run for office. Engineers seldom break into headlines except when serious accidents are attributed to faulty design' [6]. According to Wenk the main reason for this is a very simple – people ignore engineers because engineers ignore the people. But at the root of this could be various other causes – it could be the selection process, it could be also the engineers' education: 'by both inclination and preparation, many engineers approach the real world as though it were uninhabited'. Wenk also indicated the solution: a harmonisation of the natural sciences with human values and social organization, a teaching of engineering

subjects within the larger social and organizational context. It isn't clear though how this harmonisation should take place within the engineering education. However, it is doubtful that this path has been proved to be successful so far. Matthew H. Wisnioski's verdict is rather radical: the liberal education has failed [7]. His insight into the history of calls for reforms of engineering education goes back as far as 1918. After describing in detail various other approaches in this direction, including some of the most recent attempts undertaken by Caltech or MIT, Wisnioski's conclusion is pessimistic: 'It may be absurd to champion the notion of a new humanism among engineers in a society in which humanism is so self-evidently moribund and engineering so diffuse.' But one could also find a way forward in this bleak landscape. Maybe it's not only about the education, maybe it also about how the engineers see themselves, how they value the knowledge and how they understand the world. As Wisnioski put it: 'How engineers contextualize themselves in social and historical terms – how they read social knowledge to read the world—is a harder lesson, because it redirects the question set onto the self. It is one, however, that has more potential to break the frame work of an ideology of technological change.' This conclusion is leading to this study's overarching question: how engineering students are perceiving social knowledge and, based on the answer to this question, how is engineering education to be re-designed?

2 THE CHALLENGES OF INDUSTRY 4.0

2.1 Industry 4.0 – the context

The advent of the Industry 4.0 process, in which Germany and United States are leaders, shows strong potential for an increase in efficiency and productivity. The concept of Industry 4.0 — meaning the 4th industrial revolution — has become an umbrella term for a number of inter-related technologies and concepts such as the internet of things, big data, advanced analytics, additive manufacturing, and servitisation. The smart factory is one of the final products of Industry 4.0 approach. Within such smart factories, cyber-physical systems monitor the processes and make decentralized decisions. By using the internet of things, the cyber-physical systems communicate and cooperate with each other and with humans in real time. However, although Industry 4.0 concept is a top priority for many companies, research centers, and universities, there is no generally accepted understanding of this term [8]. While most of these technologies already exist, their successful integration is challenging not only from the technology perspective, but also from the human perspective. The general consensus is that new skills and competences seem to be required for this industrial leap forward.

2.2 The impact

In order to understand 'the current and future impact of key disruptions on employment level, skill sets and recruitment patterns in different industries and countries', World Economic Forum commissioned a study 'asking the Chief Human Resources Officers (CHROs) of today's largest employers to imagine how jobs in their industry will change up to the year 2020' [9]. The study was based on the assumption that there is a significant gap between today's skills requirements and future skills requirements. The understanding of the future skills requirements is crucial for the educational providers in order to close the skills gap.

Unsurprisingly, the Report foresees a significant change of the skill sets required in both old and new occupations in most industries. Moreover, the Report estimates that 'overall, social skills – such as persuasion, emotional intelligence and teaching others

– will be in higher demand across industries than narrow technical skills, such as programming or equipment operation and control. In essence, technical skills will need to be supplemented with strong social and collaboration skills’ [9]. Table 1 summarises the Report definition of social and resource management skills which are considered a part of the cross-functional category of skills.

Table 1. Definition of resource management skills and social skills, part of cross-functional skills category. Adapted from [10].

Skill/ability bundle	Skill/ability	Definition
Resource Management skills	Management of financial resources	Determining how money will be spent to get the work done, and accounting for these expenditures
	Management of material resources	Obtaining and seeing to the appropriate use of equipment, facilities and materials needed to do certain work
	People management	Motivating, developing and directing people as they work, identifying the best people for the job
	Time management	Managing one’s own time and the time of others
Social skills	Coordinating with others	Adjusting actions in relation to others’ actions
	Emotional intelligence	Being aware of other’s reactions and understanding why they react as they do
	Negotiation	Bringing others together and trying to reconcile differences
	Persuasion	Persuading others to change their minds or behavior
	Service orientation	Actively looking for ways to help people
	Training and teaching others	Teaching others how to do something

Moreover, even the basic skills category includes process skills such as ‘active listening and critical thinking’ [10]. It is expected that these skills will become a growing part of the core skills requirements for many industries. It is self-evident that most of these skills require a basic knowledge of various social sciences concepts, theories, and methods. It is also evident that understanding such elements would require a dedicated and systematic effort that goes probably further than ‘soft-skills’ and ‘global competences’ training sessions.

The question that follows is how such knowledge could be delivered and such skills could be developed in the frame of the current engineering education, especially considering the long history of similar failed attempts.

3 THE ENGINEERING STUDENTS’ PERCEPTIONS OF SOCIAL SCIENCES

3.1 Preliminary considerations

Below are few comments selected from the students’ evaluations after completing a 4th year module including consistent elements of management and social sciences, and a teaching method slightly unusual for engineering education – the case study

method. The module included elements regarding the history of specific management methods and techniques, and required students to read few articles and book chapters. The assessment was based on coursework only which consisted in a case study report.

‘Could be quite time consuming with readings’

‘Would have preferred to take other more technical and relevant modules in my final year that I could take to employers and talk about, gain more structural knowledge’

‘While some of the material on this course was useful, I question whether it should be compulsory’

‘Assessment wasn’t great - the brief was a bit too vague compared to how specifically it was marked. It wasn’t clear why this needed to be a group project, as it was just a research/lit review style essay’

While overall students’ evaluation of this particular module was rather positive, the comments section had made the author question the use of this method and turn back to the classical methods preferred by students – questions based on algorithms with unique numerical solutions. However, after careful consideration the decision taken was to investigate further the reasons for which engineering students are providing this sort of feedback. Intuitively, some general elements of students’ perception were transpiring out of the feedback:

- If there is just text, it isn’t knowledge therefore is not useful.
- It is knowledge only if it can be quantitatively measured.
- Employers want hard knowledge: software, formulas, equations, diagrams.
- Writing essay-style reports is not an appropriate activity for an engineer.

Worth mentioning that the students writing this feedback are in their final year, this meaning that they have the most mature perspective over the engineering profession a student can have. Considering all the arguments above, the author has considered that the idea of exploring engineering students’ perceptions regarding social sciences may bring some useful insights in this issue.

3.2 The exploratory study

An exploratory study has been designed consisting in a set of ten items presented in the Appendix. The students were asked to respond to a series of statements indicating the extent to which they agree with them. A five point Likert-type scale ranging from ‘Total agree’ to ‘Total disagree’ with a neutral point ‘Neither agree, nor disagree’ was used as the fixed choice response format. The academic ethical requirements and university’s procedures were strictly followed.

The study’s aim was to explore students’ perceptions regarding a number of statements reflecting few underlying hypotheses. There are 5 aspects subject of this exploratory study:

- Elements of social sciences **are useful** or rather **irrelevant** for an engineer
- The elements of social sciences should be taught **in the same way or in a different way** as all other engineering discipline,
- The elements of social sciences should be assessed **in the same way** as any other engineering discipline (e.g. questions with a single correct answer based on algorithms and formulas),

- The current curricula includes **too many** elements of social sciences, or **more such elements** would be desirable,
- The engineering degree overall result **should not** be influenced by the knowledge and understanding of elements of social sciences.

The exploratory research didn't aim for statistical relevance considering that the participation was voluntary and there was no sampling techniques used, but rather to understand how engineering students relate with these ideas. The survey was applied online to 3rd and 4th year students enrolled in engineering undergraduate programmes, respectively to students enrolled in engineering MSc programmes of a British university. The survey was emailed via a professional survey platform to approximately 300 students between 2016 and 2019. In total 65 responses were received until now and the analysis of these results is presented below.

3.3 Results

Considering the survey's exploratory nature, there have been recorded some interesting results so far. Below is the summary of these results.

1. More than two thirds (72.31%) of the respondents disagreed with the statement 'Elements of social sciences are irrelevant for an engineering career'. However, 18.47% of the respondents agreed with this statement, while 9.23% were undecided. This allows the conclusion that most of the engineering students feel that some elements of social sciences might be useful in their career, but it isn't clear which ones and more important, how could they be acquired.
2. The responses were more balanced regarding the way such elements should be taught. It appears that a majority (63.08%) of the respondents believe that social sciences are different than engineering therefore they should be taught differently than engineering disciplines. This raises the issue of understanding the differences between natural and social sciences, and their relevance and importance for an engineer.
3. The usefulness of social sciences elements for an engineering career was overwhelmingly agreed by the respondents (86.15%). This question was meant to verify the consistency of the answers to the first question. The answers are confirming the conclusion stated above – the engineering students believe that some element of social sciences could be useful.
4. A relatively small but relevant part of the respondents (20.00%) consider that the assessment of social sciences element should be done in an engineering manner - e.g. questions with a single correct answer based on algorithms and formulas, while 56.92% of the respondents disagree with this. This result suggests that the respondents tend to perceive social sciences different than technical knowledge, consequently assuming that the assessment should be also different.
5. The proportion of social sciences elements in the curricula was considered already excessive by 21.53%, while 49.23% of the respondents disagree with this statement and 29.23% are neutral. This raises the issue of introducing more social sciences elements in the engineering curricula without a proper management of students' understanding and expectations.
6. 35.38% of the respondents considered that their final result should not be influenced by their knowledge and understanding of the social sciences elements, while 43.08% of the respondents disagreed with this statement. In the context of the answers provided so far, the structure of the answers to this

item contributes to a better understanding of the engineering students' perceptions regarding social sciences knowledge. They consider that while it may be useful, it isn't a legitimate part of what they perceive to be the knowledge engineers need in order to succeed in their career.

7. Somehow in contradiction with the results so far, 80.00% of the respondents considered that some more social sciences elements would be helpful to develop skills useful for an engineer career. However, this answer might suggest a need perceived by the students to develop their skills.

The sample's structure was relatively well balanced between engineering undergraduate programmes (46.16% of the respondents) and MSc programmes (53.84%).

4 CONCLUSIONS

There are hardly reasons for optimism unless a significant change will happen in engineering education. In the current model, there are very low chances that engineering students will understand the acute need for the skills mentioned by various studies and summarised in the first part of this paper. Many of them feel that social sciences may be helpful, but they would prefer this help as non-compulsory training sessions, eventually not assessed. The differences between social sciences and natural sciences are not well understood, so is the impact of social sciences on individual skills that may be very useful in the near future. The respondents considered that social sciences could be relevant and useful for engineers, and the teaching and assessment of such element should be done rather different than in the case of engineering disciplines. Eventually some more elements could be added, but a large share of the respondents considers that their final award should not be influenced by the knowledge of these elements.

Hopefully, engineering curricula could be re-designed so more relevant elements of the social sciences will be introduced to address directly the knowledge and skills required by the Industry 4.0. But before this re-design, there is an acute need to understand why social sciences knowledge keeps failing in the engineering education. Based on the results of this exploratory survey, it can be argued that it isn't only the curricula content and structure, it is also the perceptions of the engineering students that contribute to this record of failures. The improvement of this poor record would require a significant change of both, perhaps with a greater emphasis placed on the later.

In conclusion it is essential to revisit not only the content and how social sciences knowledge is delivered to engineering students, but also how their expectations regarding what makes a good engineer are informed and managed.

5 LIMITATIONS AND FURTHER RESEARCH

As it was already mentioned, this paper presents the results of a study aiming to explore engineering students' perceptions regarding social sciences. The lack of representativeness is the major limitation which usually characterises any exploratory research. Therefore there is no base to assume that these results are valid for all engineering students. However, the results open few potentially seminal avenues that might provide helpful insights into the main challenges faced by the engineering education required by Industry 4.0 technology progress.

Further research will need to understand how engineering students understanding of the social sciences is produced and how it can be managed according to the industry's requirements. This demands a better understanding of how the dichotomy between social science and natural sciences is informed before the students even start their higher education journey. If this dichotomy is produced before the university, it will require a solid strategy to address it adequately.

Another future research should look into how the general skills described by various reports as required by the technologies of the future are translated into specific components. It is unclear how much of the skills described in Table 1 requires knowledge that could be acquired by the classic learning process and how much is developed by training or by using other teaching methods. This ambiguity contributes to the students' state of relative confusion regarding what constitutes social sciences and how this type of knowledge and skills could be acquired and should be assessed.

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Appendix

Survey

Please express your agreement with the following statements on a scale from **-2 (total disagreement)** to **+2 (total agreement)**

Important note: there are no correct or wrong answers. It is very important to understand your perception regarding the importance of social sciences in engineering.

Definitions:

In the understanding of this survey, **social sciences** include: sociology, psychology, economics, anthropology, management, organisation studies.

By **elements of social sciences**, we mean concepts (e.g. free market, motivation, behaviour, organisation, social group), theories (e.g. hierarchy of needs, neo-liberalism) and methods (e.g. cost-benefit, interview, personality test, case study) that were developed in one of social sciences.

1. Elements of social sciences **are irrelevant** for an engineering career, because some people are born with social skills, some other are born without social skills, and the employers are interested in engineering knowledge rather than social skills
2. The elements of social sciences should be taught **in the same way** as all other engineering discipline, because all of them are part of science.
3. The elements of social sciences should be taught **differently** than other engineering discipline, because social sciences are different than engineering and natural sciences
4. Elements of social sciences **are very useful** for an engineering career because they help me understand better the human behaviour and help me develop the skills required to succeed in an organisation
5. The elements of social sciences should be assessed **in the same way** as any other engineering discipline (e.g. questions with a single correct answer based on algorithms and formulas)
6. The current curricula includes **too many** such elements of social sciences, I would like to have more engineering elements instead
7. My engineering degree overall result **should not** be influenced by my knowledge and understanding of elements of social sciences, because I'm trained to be an engineer
8. Some **more** elements of social sciences would help develop skills an engineer needs in her/his career, because such skills could be developed and improved

Please indicate the programme category you're enrolled in (choose between BEng, MEng and MSc)